

DETERMINANTS OF SOCIAL COMMERCE INTENTION AND THEIR IMPACT ON ACTUAL USE BEHAVIOR

Ganguli Ranasinghe¹, Amitha Kumara², Sanduni Senaratne³
Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce
University of Sri Jayewardenepura

¹ganguranasinghe97@gmail.com, ²amitha@sjp.ac.lk, ³sanduni@sjp.ac.lk

Introduction

The combination of Electronic Commerce (e-commerce), web 2.0 technologies, and social networking sites (SNSs) such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and WhatsApp paved the way for the emergence of Social Commerce (SC) as a new paradigm under e-commerce (Busalim and Hussin, 2016). An article published by Forbes stated that 30% of consumers purchase products and services through SNSs to fulfil their needs (Arnold, 2018). Therefore, we can identify that ‘Social Commerce’ is now becoming a popular segment in today’s e-commerce context. Scholars have investigated social commerce in different aspects, most of which identified factors affecting social commerce intention (Grange, Benbasat and Burton-jones, 2018; Hettiarachchi, Wickramasinghe and Ranathunga, 2018).

Social commerce allows consumers to perform buying and selling transactions, compare and share their experiences, and recommend products and services to others with the help of SNSs through Social Commerce Constructs (SCCs). Ratings and reviews, forums and communities, recommendations and referrals were identified as the main SCCs (Sheikh et al., 2019). Maintaining long-lasting relationships with consumers will help businesses to increase their customer loyalty and secure their market share. This is identified as Relationship Quality, and scholars identified it as an important factor that affects social commerce intention (Wang and Hajli, 2014; Tajvidi et al., 2021). According to the previous studies, Relationship Quality was measured using commitment, satisfaction, and trust (Liang et al., 2011; Sheikh et al., 2019). Further,

Social Support in social commerce allows users to gain new knowledge and experiences that support them in making informed and accurate purchase decisions (Hajli, 2014). Emotional Support and Informational Support are the two main dimensions of Social support in the digital context (Liang et al., 2011). Literature has revealed that social support considerably impacts social commerce intention (Liang et al., 2011; Wang and Hajli, 2014).

However, when considering a sample which has prior experience in social commerce, there is a lack of studies focusing on online social support, relationship quality and SCCs in determining the social commerce intention and the actual use of Social Commerce (Sheikh et al., 2019). In the Sri Lankan context, a few research studies were undertaken to investigate this Social Commerce domain, but they were limited to a general sample without considering the actual users of Social Commerce (Hettiarachchi, Wickramasinghe and Ranathunga, 2018; Samarasinghe and Silva, 2019).

Thus, the main objectives of this study were to identify the factors affecting Social Commerce Intention and to identify the impact of Intention on Actual Use Behavior. This study proposed a conceptual framework developed based on social support theory, relationship marketing theory, and information systems (IS) related literature (Sheikh et al., 2019).

Methodology

The conceptual framework of the study was developed based on a previous study done by Sheikh et al. (2019).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Six hypotheses were formulated based on the literature. A deductive approach in quantitative research methodology (Sheikh et al., 2019) was used in this study. The survey method was used to collect data from the respondents using an online questionnaire. The online questionnaire consists of question items that were validated previously. Sri Lankan consumers who have prior experience in social commerce were the population, and the sample to conduct the study was selected following the snowballing technique. Descriptive data analysis of the findings was performed using the SPSS software, and validating the measurement model and the structural model, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) through Partial Least Squares (PLS) estimation was used.

Results and Discussion

A total of 102 valid responses were used for the analysis after screening. The majority of the respondents (69.61%) were in the age category of 21-25 years, and 50.98% of the respondents were males. Further, all the respondents have at least one social media account and mostly used SNSs were Facebook and WhatsApp.

The measurement model was tested for the reliability and validity of the constructs. According to Hair, Ringle and Sarstedt (2011), the minimum

threshold value for indicator reliability is 0.7, and there were few questionnaire items with low factor loadings. Since the removal of those items did not increase the threshold values of internal consistency and reliability, and thus deletion of the items was not performed (Hair et al., 2017). According to the measurement model analysis results, criteria for internal consistency and reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity of the constructs were met. (Fornell and Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2017).

Structural model analysis was done using SmartPLS software (Sheikh et al., 2019). The results of the R-square (R²) indicated that 27% of the variance in the actual use behavior of social commerce was caused by the social commerce intention, indicating that the model has a satisfactory level of explanatory power.

Table 1. Summary of Hypotheses Testing Results

Hypothesis	Path	Path Coefficient	P-Values	Study Results
H1	SCI ▼ UB	0.519	0.000***	Supported
H2	RQ ▼ SCI	0.265	0.035*	Supported
H3a	SCC▼ SCI	0.201	0.195	Not Supported
H3b	SCC▼ RQ	0.313	0.004**	Supported
H4a	SS ▼ SCI	0.318	0.019*	Supported
H4b	SS ▼ RQ	0.449	0.000***	Supported

*Note: *Significant at $P < 0.05$ **Significant at $P < 0.01$ ***Significant at $P < 0.001$*

According to the findings, the social commerce intention has a significant positive impact on the actual user behavior in social commerce, confirming the findings of Sheikh et al. (2019). This implied that there is a high possibility of consumers using social commerce to make their purchases through SNSs if they have intentions to buy online. The findings also revealed that the relationship quality in SNSs positively impacts social commerce intention, agreeing with the findings of Liang et al. (2011) and Sheikh et al. (2019).

However, contrary to the expectations, social commerce constructs do not positively impact social commerce intention, contrasting to the findings of Hajli and Sims (2015) and Sheikh et al. (2019). This implied that the respondents of the current research context do not consider the value generated through the availability of social commerce constructs on their intention to purchase in social commerce.

The results also indicated that social commerce constructs have a significant positive impact on relationship quality, which is consistent with the findings of Wang and Hajli (2014) and Sheikh et al. (2019). SCCs can improve consumers' relationship quality with SNSs, which leads consumers to trust SNSs and the sellers who use social commerce. Facilities such as the availability of different online social platforms and communities and the ability to interact with other consumers in such settings allow for generating higher relationship quality.

The findings also indicated that social support positively affects social commerce intention. This confirms the findings of Liang et al. (2011), Hajli (2014) and Sheikh et al. (2019). To obtain pre-purchase information about products/services, consumers use different SNSs and online communities. Most consumers are also willing to share their experiences and support others by providing informational and emotional support.

Finally, this study revealed that social support has a significant positive impact on relationship quality, which is in line with the findings of Liang et al. (2011) and Sheikh et al. (2019). The supportive environment developed for sharing information, knowledge, and experiences among consumers, with the help of informational and emotional support, increases the relationship quality.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to identify the factors affecting Social Commerce Intention and the impact of Intention on Actual Use Behavior. A conceptual model was developed based on social support theory, relationship

marketing theory, and IS-related literature (Sheikh et al., 2019) to achieve the above purposes.

The findings of this study highlighted that social support and relationship quality available on SNSs are the significant factors that affect consumers' intention to purchase in social commerce. The use of social support theory along with the relationship quality from relationship marketing theory is a key contribution of this study. It helps to determine the intention, which finally leads to the actual use of social commerce.

This study suggested that businesses should create more virtual communities, which consumers can join later using SNSs. Enhanced social support received from communities in SNSs will help consumers to make more informed purchase decisions. This will also help businesses to develop and maintain healthy and long-lasting relationships with their consumers. Since the relationship quality with SNSs positively affects on social commerce intention, businesses should pay attention to the trustworthiness of their social commerce platforms to provide consumers with more trust and satisfaction.

However, the proposed conceptual model was validated only by using a smaller sample that used social commerce in Sri Lanka. Since most of the respondents were also in the age category of 21-25 years, the results may only reflect their preference. Therefore, future researchers are encouraged to consider a larger sample to get better insights by reaching respondents from other age groups.

References

Arnold, A. (2018) *Are We Entering The Era Of Social Shopping?*, *Forbes*. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/andrewarnold/2018/04/04/are-we-entering-the-era-of-social-shopping/>.

Busalim, A. H. and Hussin, A. R. C. (2016) 'Understanding social commerce: A systematic literature review and directions for further research', *International Journal of Information Management*. Elsevier Ltd, 36(6), pp. 1075–1088. doi: 10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2016.06.005.

Fornell, C. and Larcker, D. F. (1981) 'Evaluating Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error', *Journal of Marketing Research*, XVIII(February), pp. 39–50.

Grange, C., Benbasat, I. and Burton-jones, A. (2018) 'A Network-Based Conceptualization of Social Commerce and Social Commerce Value', *Computers in Human Behavior*. Elsevier B.V., 108. doi: 10.1016/j.chb.2018.12.033.

Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M. and Sarstedt, M. (2017) *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. 2nd Editio. Sage Publications, Inc.

Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M. and Sarstedt, M. (2011) 'PLS-SEM : Indeed a Silver Bullet', *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 19(2), pp. 139–151. doi: 10.2753/MTP1069-6679190202.

Hajli, M. N. (2014) 'The role of social support on relationship quality and social commerce', *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*. Elsevier Inc., 87, pp. 17–27. doi: 10.1016/j.techfore.2014.05.012.

Hajli, N. and Sims, J. (2015) 'Social commerce : The transfer of power from sellers to buyers', *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*. Elsevier Inc., 94, pp. 350–358. doi: 10.1016/j.techfore.2015.01.012.

Hettiarachchi, H. A. H., Wickramasinghe, C. N. and Ranathunga, S. (2018) 'The Influence of Social Commerce on Consumer Decisions', *The International Technology Management Review*, 7(1), pp. 47–58.

Liang, T. P., Ho, Y. T., Li, Y. W. and Turban, E. (2011) 'What drives social commerce: The role of social support and relationship quality', *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 16(2), pp. 69–90. doi: 10.2753/JEC1086-4415160204.

Samarasinghe, S. and Silva, K. (2019) ‘Social Commerce Acceptance : Integrated Model with Collaboration Theories and Technology Acceptance Model’, *American Scientific Research Journal for Engineering, Technology, and Sciences (ASRJETS)*, 62(1), pp. 39–53.

Sheikh, Z., Yezheng, L., Islam, T., Hameed, Z. and Khan, I. U. (2019) ‘Impact of social commerce constructs and social support on social commerce intentions’, *Information Technology and People*, 32(1), pp. 68–93. doi: 10.1108/ITP-04-2018-0195.

Tajvidi, M., Wang, Y., Hajli, N. and Love, P. E. D. (2021) ‘Brand value Co-creation in social commerce: The role of interactivity, social support, and relationship quality’, *Computers in Human Behavior*. Elsevier Ltd., 115. doi: 10.1016/j.chb.2017.11.006.

Wang, Y. and Hajli, M. N. (2014) ‘Co-creation in branding through social commerce: The role of social support, relationship quality and privacy concerns’, in *20th Americas Conference on Information Systems, AMCIS 2014*. Savannah, Georgia, pp. 1–16. Available at: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=2449127>.